
Corroboration of the Quadrants Within the Cartesian Coordinate System to Justify Whether Clockwise Movement or Anticlockwise Movement During the Resolution

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Abstract

The quadrants movement within the Cartesian coordinate system is of utmost importance when resolving vectors, working in trigonometry, geometry, bearings and performing other mathematical functions. It is well justified and established fact that movement of the quadrant from quadrant I to quadrant IV is anticlockwise. This research is to investigate and justify that the movement is also clockwise when moving from quadrant I ($0 - \frac{\pi}{2}$) to quadrant IV ($\frac{3\pi}{2} - 2\pi$). The resolution of vectors to obtain vertical and horizontal components is used to obtain values in the x – direction and Y – direction in each of the quadrant. This is then analyzed to see the trigonometry ratios (sine, cosine and tan) signs for each of the four quadrants either being positive or negative. After analysis, it is well established that quadrant movement and position is justified or corroborated with clockwise movement just like anticlockwise movement. The anticlockwise movement or direction is internationally accepted and hence being compared to clockwise movement or direction which is same as the direction of the second, minute and hour hand of a clock. Clockwise resolution is also justified as in moment of forces and the movement of the blades of a ceiling fan.

Keywords: quadrant, Cartesian, coordinate system, sine, cosine, tan, vectors, clockwise, anticlockwise, trigonometry, bearing.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Cartesian coordinate system

The Cartesian coordinate system is a general representation of coordinates of any point in space. When a two dimensional (2D) system is considered, thus x -axis and y -axis, any object or point may be located by measuring from the origin using any unit of measurement one finds or deem fit for the process. The origin (0, 0) of the Cartesian coordinate system is the point of intersection from positive X (from the East) to negative X (to the west) and from positive Y (from the North) to the negative Y (to the South). The system of locating points on a Cartesian graph is made up of drawing a straight horizontal line called x - axis and a vertical perpendicular line called y – axis crossing the x – axis. And the point of intersection is called the origin (0, 0). The axis (x and y) may then be divided and numbered using any unit or factor the mathematician deems fit for his graph work. Points are located within a quadrant as ordered pairs for instance; (0, 0) is the origin and (2, 4), (-3, 9), (-3,-5), (8,-5) are all ordered pairs representing an x – value and y -value i.e. (X , Y). The first of the two pairs is the x – coordinate and the second of the pair is the y – coordinate. These ordered pairs can either be found within a quadrant (I to IV) or on the axis (+ve X , -ve X , +ve Y and -ve Y) of the Cartesian coordinate system. The ordered pairs can also be found on the line seen as x -axis (in this case all values y on the x – axis are zero). For instance, (2,0), (3,0), (5,0), (-3,0), (-9,0). Again, the ordered pairs can

also be found on the line seen as y -axis (in this case all values x on the y -axis are zero). Examples includes (0, 3), (0,-6), (0, 5), (0,-6) etc. Consider clockwise movement, quadrant I (QI) will have ordered pairs like (2, 4), (1, 3), (4, 5) etc. Quadrant II (QII) will have ordered pairs such as (3, -4), (4, -6), (2, -7), (1,-3) and so on. Quadrant III (QIII) will have ordered pairs such as (-2, -2), (-2, -8), (-4, -2), (-6,-3) and so one. And the last quadrant which is quadrant IV (QIV) will have order pairs such as (-1, 3), (-5, 8), (-5, 5), (-2, 6), (-7, 8) etc. Ordered pairs are what justify a point on a graph within the Cartesian coordinate system. The ordered pairs generated for the quadrant above will not be the same for anticlockwise movement (Q1 – QIV).

1.2 Quadrant system

For coordinate geometry analysis and concept, quadrants are very important in order to identify the first, second, third and fourth quadrant either through clockwise movement or anticlockwise movement. Also while plotting a graph on a 2-D graph paper, one ought to know about graph quadrants. Furthermore, the two intersecting lines (X and Y) in the Cartesian plane make four distinct graph quadrants. This x -axis and y -axis of a graph divide it into four quadrants. Moreover, each quadrant includes a combination of positive and negative values for coordinates x and y . The coordinate plane or Cartesian plane is a basic concept but essential for coordinate geometry. Furthermore, a two-dimensional graph is known as a Cartesian plane. It includes negative and positive values of both x and y . Thus a graph is divided into four quadrants, or sections, on the basis of those values.

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1.2.1 Graph Quadrant for anticlockwise movement

Movement within the Cartesian coordinate system can be either clockwise movement in nature or anticlockwise. Clockwise movement is from positive Y - axis to positive X to negative Y to negative X and back to positive Y. And the reverse direction or movement is said to be anticlockwise. Such movements establish the quadrant system from quadrant I to quadrant IV. That is from positive Y - axis to negative X to negative Y to positive X – axis and back to positive Y - axis.

Quadrant I: The first quadrant is available in the upper right-hand corner of the plane. Both x and y happen to consist of positive values in this quadrant. Angle measurement is from $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ ($0 - \frac{\pi}{2}$).

Quadrant II: The second quadrant happens to be in the upper left-hand corner of the plane. Moreover, X has negative values in this quadrant and y has positive values. Angle measurement is from $90^\circ - 180^\circ$ ($\frac{\pi}{2} - \pi$).

Quadrant III: The third quadrant is in the bottom left corner of the plane. Furthermore, both x and y have negative values in this quadrant. Angle measurement is from $180^\circ - 270^\circ$ ($\pi - \frac{3\pi}{2}$).

Quadrant IV: The fourth quadrant is in the bottom right corner of the plane. In this coordinate, X has positive values and y has negative values. Angle measurement is from $270^\circ - 360^\circ$ ($\frac{3\pi}{2} - 2\pi$).

Fig 1: Quadrant Positions on a graph for anticlockwise movement (Source: www.splashlearn.com)

1.2.2 Graph Quadrant for clockwise movement

Quadrant I: The first quadrant is available in the upper right-hand corner of the plane. Both x and y happen to consist of positive values in this quadrant. Angle measurement is from $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ ($0 - \frac{\pi}{2}$).

Quadrant II: The second quadrant is in the bottom right corner of the plane. In this coordinate X has positive values and y has negative values. Angle measurement is from $90^\circ - 180^\circ$ ($\frac{\pi}{2} - \pi$).

Quadrant III: The third quadrant is in the bottom left corner of the plane. Furthermore, both x and y have negative values in this quadrant. Angle measurement is from $180^\circ - 270^\circ (\pi - \frac{3\pi}{2})$.

Quadrant IV: The fourth quadrant happens to be in the upper left-hand corner of the plane. Moreover, X has negative values in this quadrant and y has positive values. Angle measurement is from $270^\circ - 360^\circ (\frac{3\pi}{2} - 2\pi)$.

Fig 2: Quadrant Positions on a graph for clockwise movement

This is how quadrants (I to IV) are defined and determined on a graph within the Cartesian coordinates system. This research work is therefore sorting to investigate whether the quadrant position and movement can also be in the clockwise direction. In

that quadrant I will be $0 - \frac{\pi}{2}$, quadrant II will be $\frac{\pi}{2} - \pi$, quadrant III will be $\pi - \frac{3\pi}{2}$ and quadrant IV being $\frac{3\pi}{2} - 2\pi$.

Table 1: Ordered pairs within a quadrant

Quadrant	Clockwise Movement (Angle in Rad)	Anticlockwise Movement (Angle in Rad)	Clockwise Movement (X,Y) Value	Anticlockwise Movement (X, Y) Value
I	$0 - \frac{\pi}{2}$	$0 - \frac{\pi}{2}$	(+, +)	(+,+)
II	$\frac{\pi}{2} - \pi$	$\frac{\pi}{2} - \pi$	(+, -)	(-,+)
III	$\pi - \frac{3\pi}{2}$	$\pi - \frac{3\pi}{2}$	(-, -)	(-, -)
IV	$\frac{3\pi}{2} - 2\pi$	$\frac{3\pi}{2} - 2\pi$	(-, +)	(+, -)

1.3 Angles Determination within quadrants

Determination of quadrants from I to IV within the Cartesian coordinate system is bounded within some angles. Angles in quadrant I falls within the range $0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, quadrant II have the angles in the range $\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq \pi$, quadrant III is in the range of $\pi \leq \theta \leq \frac{3\pi}{2}$ and quadrant IV falls within the range $\frac{3\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$. The range of values for each of the quadrant on a range of $0 - 90$ is $0^\circ - 90^\circ$ which per angles system, is a right angle triangle. To be able to obtain an angle within a quadrant, a right angle triangle needs to be drawn. This shows that a specific angle within the quadrant can never be found or determined unless a line has been drawn from the origin (0, 0) of the Cartesian plane

to a point say (a, b) to obtain two right angle triangles, let's say angles θ and ϕ as seen in **Fig. 3**. With a known value for the hypotenuse (R), it can then be resolved to obtain the horizontal component (H_x) and vertical component (V_y). The quadrant within which the resolution occurred is then used to determine whether X is positive or negative and whether Y is positive or negative.

Fig 3: Angles in a quadrant determination

Resolving to obtain the horizontal and vertical component mainly depends on the trigonometry ratios of sine and cosine for angles θ° and ϕ° and vice versa. The values obtained for the H_x and V_x should be the same for both angles but manipulation with different trigonometric ratios of sine and cosine. With this

method of determining angles within a quadrant, the same results of H_x and V_y is obtained for different quadrants (I to IV) but with different signs (positive or negative) defined by the quadrant under review.

2 Research Approach

It is well established that quadrant determination and movement within the Cartesian coordinate system is anticlockwise from quadrant I to quadrant IV. Angles in quadrant I falls within the range $0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, quadrant II have the angles in the range $\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq \pi$, quadrant III is in the range $\pi \leq \theta \leq \frac{3\pi}{2}$ and quadrant IV falls within the range $\frac{3\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$. The angles ranges are correct, same and applicable for clockwise rotation or movement on the Cartesian coordinate system just like the second, minute and hour hand of a clock clockwise movement. Hence with the believe and motion that quadrant movement and rotation on the Cartesian coordinate system ought to be clockwise movement or rotation. This research work is therefore using vectors resolution, trigonometry ratios, and Pythagoras theorem to investigate and corroborate that quadrant determination and positions on the Cartesian coordinate system is clockwise movement in nature just like the second, minute, hour hand of a clock, ceiling fan and in moment of forces. As can be seen in **fig 4**, there are four quadrants (QI – QIV). But one cannot use just the quadrant to obtain the horizontal and vertical component within the quadrant except having angles less than $\frac{\pi}{2}$. If not so, it will give a square or rectangle which is not applicable when dealing with Pythagoras theorem and trigonometry ratios. Therefore the quadrant is divided into two so that the sum of the two angles is

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equal to $\frac{\pi}{2}$ ($\theta + \phi = 90^\circ$) as in **fig 3**. With this θ° and ϕ° , two right angles triangles are obtained to resolve into horizontal component (x-value) and vertical component (y-value). Resolving to obtain the horizontal component (H_x) and vertical component (V_y) depends on the trigonometry ratios of sine and cosine for angles θ° and ϕ° and vice versa. The values obtained for the H_x and V_y should be the same for both angles but manipulation with different trigonometric ratios of sine and cosine. With this method of determining angles within a quadrant, the same results of H_x and V_y is obtained for different quadrants (QI to QIV) but with different signs (positive or negative) defined by x – axis and y – axis by the quadrant under review as detailed in results and discussions.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Clockwise movement Analysis

Fig 4: Resolving for horizontal (H_x) and vertical (V_y) components in each quadrant (I – IV) moving clockwise

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Table 2: Angles Used in the analysis for each quadrants (QI – QIV)

Quadrant	Clockwise Movement	Anticlockwise Movement
I	(60°) and (30°)	60°) and (30°)
II	150°	120°
III	210°	240°
IV	330°	300°

Table 2 gives a clear indication of the angles used for resolving the resultant vector 2 as in Fig 4 and Fig 5 to obtain the horizontal component (H_x) and vertical component (V_y) using the angles obtained in each of the quadrants (I – IV).

Fig 5: Referral triangle for resolving into horizontal and vertical components

For quadrant 1, Q1 (60° and 30°)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 60 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\cos 60 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= 1 \\ \sin 60 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\sin 60 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \cos 30 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\cos 30 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \sin 30 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\sin 30 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= 1 \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{\sin 30}{\cos 30} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sin 60}{\cos 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\tan 60 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{1}$$

$$\tan 60 = \sqrt{3}$$

Therefore in quadrant 1, Q1

$$\sin = +$$

$$\cos = +$$

$$\tan = +$$

Quadrant II, QII (150°)

$$\cos 60 = \frac{x}{2}$$

$$x = 2\cos 60$$

$$x = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$x = 1$$

$$\sin 60 = \frac{y}{2}$$

$$y = 2\sin 60$$

$$y = 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = -\sqrt{3}$$

$$\cos 30 = \frac{y}{2}$$

$$y = 2\cos 30$$

$$y = 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = -\sqrt{3}$$

$$\sin 30 = \frac{x}{2}$$

$$x = 2\sin 30$$

$$x = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$x = 1$$

$$\text{Tan } 30 = \frac{\text{Sin}30}{\text{Cos}30}$$

$$\text{tan}30 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$$\text{Tan } 60 = \frac{\text{Sin}60}{\text{Cos}60}$$

$$\text{tan}60 = \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{1}$$

$$\text{tan}60 = -\sqrt{3}$$

Therefore for quadrant II, (150°)

$$\text{Cos} = +$$

$$\text{Sin} = -$$

$$\text{Cos} = -$$

$$\text{Sin} = +$$

$$\text{Tan} = -$$

$$\text{Tan} = -$$

For Quadrant III (210°)

$$\text{Sin } 30 = \frac{x}{2}$$

$$x = 2\text{Sin}30$$

$$x = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$x = -1$$

$$\text{Cos } 30 = \frac{y}{2}$$

$$y = 2\text{Cos}30$$

$$y = 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = -\sqrt{3}$$

$$\text{Cos } 60 = \frac{x}{2}$$

$$x = 2\text{Cos}60$$

$$x = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$x = -1$$

$$\text{Sin } 60 = \frac{y}{2}$$

$$y = 2\text{Sin}60$$

$$y = 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = -\sqrt{3}$$

$$\text{Tan } 30 = \frac{\text{Sin}30}{\text{Cos}30}$$

$$\text{tan}30 = \frac{-1}{-\sqrt{3}}$$

$$\text{tan}30 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$$\text{Tan } 60 = \frac{\text{Sin}60}{\text{Cos}60}$$

$$\text{tan}60 = \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{-1}$$

$$\text{tan}60 = \sqrt{3}$$

Therefore for quadrant III, (210°)

$$\text{Cos} = -$$

$$\text{Sin} = -$$

$$\text{Cos} = -$$

$$\sin = -$$

$$\tan = +$$

$$\tan = +$$

For quadrant IV, Q IV (330°)

$$\cos 60 = \frac{x}{2}$$

$$x = 2\cos 60$$

$$x = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$x = -1$$

$$\sin 60 = \frac{y}{2}$$

$$y = 2\sin 60$$

$$y = 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = \sqrt{3}$$

$$\sin 30 = \frac{x}{2}$$

$$x = 2\sin 30$$

$$x = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$x = -1$$

$$\cos 30 = \frac{y}{2}$$

$$y = 2\cos 30$$

$$y = 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = \sqrt{3}$$

$$\tan 30 = \frac{\sin 30}{\cos 30}$$

$$\tan 30 = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$$\tan 30 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$$\tan 60 = \frac{\sin 60}{\cos 60}$$

$$\tan 60 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{-1}$$

$$\tan 60 = -\sqrt{3}$$

Therefore for quadrant IV, (330°)

$$\cos = -$$

$$\sin = +$$

$$\cos = +$$

$$\sin = -$$

$$\tan = -$$

$$\tan = -$$

3.2 Anticlockwise movement analysis

Fig 6: Resolving for horizontal (x) and vertical (y) components in each quadrant (I – IV) moving anticlockwise

For quadrant 1, Q1 (60° and 30°)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 60 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\cos 60 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= 1 \\ \sin 60 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\sin 60 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \cos 30 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\cos 30 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \sin 30 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\sin 30 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tan 30 &= \frac{\sin 30}{\cos 30} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sin 60}{\cos 60} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{1} \\ \tan 60 &= \sqrt{3} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore in quadrant 1, Q1

$$\begin{aligned} \sin &= + \\ \cos &= + \\ \tan &= + \end{aligned}$$

Quadrant II, QII (120°)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 60 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\cos 60 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= -1 \\ \sin 60 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\sin 60 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \cos 30 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\cos 30 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \sin 30 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\sin 30 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= -1 \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{\sin 30}{\cos 30} \\ \tan 30 &= -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sin 60}{\cos 60} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tan 60 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{-1} \\ \tan 60 &= -\sqrt{3} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore for quadrant II, (120°)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos &= + \\ \sin &= - \\ \cos &= - \\ \sin &= + \\ \tan &= - \\ \tan &= - \end{aligned}$$

For Quadrant III, QIII (240°)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 60 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\cos 60 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= -1 \\ \sin 60 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\sin 60 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= -\sqrt{3} \\ \sin 30 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\sin 30 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= -1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cos 30 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\cos 30 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{\sin 30}{\cos 30} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sin 60}{\cos 60} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{1} \\ \tan 60 &= \sqrt{3} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore for quadrant III, QIII (240°)

$$\begin{aligned} \cos &= - \\ \sin &= - \\ \cos &= - \\ \sin &= - \\ \tan &= + \\ \tan &= + \end{aligned}$$

For quadrant IV, QIV (300°)

$$\begin{aligned} \sin 30 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\sin 30 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 1 \\ \cos 30 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\cos 30 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \cos 60 &= \frac{x}{2} \\ x &= 2\cos 60 \\ x &= 2 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ x &= 1 \\ \sin 60 &= \frac{y}{2} \\ y &= 2\sin 60 \\ y &= 2 \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ y &= \sqrt{3} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{\sin 30}{\cos 30} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 30 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sin 60}{\cos 60} \\ \tan 60 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{1} \\ \tan 60 &= \sqrt{3} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore for quadrant IV, QIV (300°)

- $\text{Cos} = -$
- $\text{Sin} = +$
- $\text{Cos} = +$
- $\text{Sin} = -$
- $\text{Tan} = -$
- $\text{Tan} = -$

3.3 Calculator Justification for some Resultant Resolution
Table 3: 150° clockwise and 120° anticlockwise resolution and calculator justification

Clockwise	+/-	Anticlockwise	+/-
Sin 150°	+	Sin 120°	+
Cos 150°	-	Cos 120°	-

Fig 7: Clockwise resolution for 150° .

Fig 8: Anticlockwise resolution for 120° .

Fig 8: Properties of angles

Fig 7 and Fig 8 gives the result for the resolution of 150° angle clockwise (I – IV) and 120° angle anticlockwise (I – IV) as seen in the result in Table 3. Fig. 9 shows the properties of angles to justify the angles resolution and a final confirmation with the calculator. From the understanding of angles properties as in Fig. 9, resolving 150° angle clockwise to obtain the horizontal and vertical component (X and Y) is the same as resolving for 120° angle anticlockwise for the horizontal and vertical components. The answers obtained for the X component and Y component are both positive and negative for both clockwise movement and anticlockwise moment. The calculator does justify the answers for clockwise resolution to correspond to the natural or already accepted Cartesian coordinate graph system accepted internationally just like for anticlockwise movement as depicted in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

3. Discussion of results

Results obtained above gives a clear indication of the final results for every horizontal component (H_x or x) and vertical component (V_y or y) obtained after resolving the Resultant value (2) – per calculator usage in each of the quadrants for the angles shown in Table 2. Table 3 is depicting the sign status (Positive or negative) for the three trigonometry ratios (sine, cosine and tangent) under consideration obtained in each of the quadrants (I – IV). It can clearly be seen that resolving in each quadrants gives the same trigonometry ratios sign and results for both clockwise movement of the quadrant within the Cartesian coordinate system and for

anticlockwise movement of the quadrants in the Cartesian coordinate system. It can be seen that for the clockwise movement from quadrant I (QI) to quadrant IV (QIV), the acronym ALL SILLY TOM CAT is obeyed and for anticlockwise movement from quadrant I (QI) to quadrant IV (QIV), the acronym ALL SCIENCE TEACHERS CRAZY is also obeyed. In all the cases of the acronym, All in quadrant 1 (QI) means sine and cosec are positive, cosine and sec are positive and tangent and cot are positive. For the SILLY and SCIENCE in quadrant II (QII), only sine and cosec are positive, cosine, sec, tan and cot are negatives. TOM and Teachers in quadrant III (QIII) is justified as positive for only tan and cot. Sine, cosec, cosine and sec are all negatives. CAT and CRAZY justifies cosine and sec as the only positive trigonometry ratios in quadrant IV (QIV) as depicted in Table 3. Sine, cosec, tan and cot all are negatives in the fourth quadrant. This show that quadrant movement and position is justified or corroborated with clockwise movement just like anticlockwise movement which is internationally accepted comparable to the direction of the second, minute and hour hand of a clock, blades of a ceiling fan and is clearly depicted in Table 3. But I think the quadrant movement should follow a natural course like the second, minute and hour hand of a clock, blades of ceiling.

The calculator does justify answers to corresponds to the natural or already accepted Cartesian coordinate graph system accepted internationally just like for clockwise movement and anticlockwise movement as depicted in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. As can be seen above, resolving angle 120° and

150⁰ to obtain the horizontal component both clockwise and anticlockwise does give the same values. Clockwise rotation gives a positive value for H_x which is true as x is positive.

Table 4: Determining whether sine, cosine or tangent is positive or negative within a quadrant

Quadrant	Clockwise movement	Anticlockwise Movement
I	All +Ve	All +Ve
II	$\cos = +$ $\sin = -$ $\cos = -$ $\sin = +$ $\tan = -$ $\tan = -$	$\cos = +$ $\sin = -$ $\cos = -$ $\sin = +$ $\tan = -$ $\tan = -$
III	$\cos = -$ $\sin = -$ $\cos = -$ $\sin = -$ $\tan = +$ $\tan = +$	$\cos = -$ $\sin = -$ $\cos = -$ $\sin = -$ $\tan = +$ $\tan = +$
IV	$\cos = -$ $\sin = +$ $\cos = +$ $\sin = -$ $\tan = -$ $\tan = -$	$\cos = -$ $\sin = +$ $\cos = +$ $\sin = -$ $\tan = -$ $\tan = -$

4 Conclusion

The Cartesian coordinate system having the x –axis and y – axis gives four quadrants (I – IV) when both axis crosses each other. The point of intersection is called the origin (0, 0). A quadrant is the area contained by the x and y axes, thus, there are four quadrants in any graph system. The two dimensional Cartesian plane is divided by x - axis and y - axes into four quadrants. Starting in the top right corner is quadrant I and in anticlockwise movement or direction moves to quadrant II through to IV. This research has also justified that quadrant position and direction can be seen to be in a clockwise movement or direction from quadrant I to quadrant IV. This show that quadrant movement and position is justified or corroborated with clockwise movement just like anticlockwise movement which is internationally accepted. The clockwise movement is comparable to the direction of the second, minute, hour hand of a clock, the blades of ceiling fan. This same clockwise movement is again justified and likened to movement in resolution of forces. By the normal graph system, from +ve X– axis to –ve Y – axis, and from –ve Y –axis to -ve X – axis and from –ve X - axis to +ve Y – axis movement within the Cartesian coordinates system is clockwise. And this should be natural course of direction. This does not balance with the anticlockwise movement from quadrant 1 (Q1) to quadrant (Q4).

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